

MAIN STAGES OF SPEECH GENERATION

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Anotation

The article analyzes theories about the generation, occurrence of speech in a child, which are widely used in modern linguistics. In particular, the views of foreign scientists (Russian, European, American) about the psycho-cognitive processes that are the root cause of the generation of speech acts by a child are examined. A comparative analysis of speech generation models is given.

Keywords

speech generation, child's speech, model, development, psyche, cognitive process, internal and external speech, thinking, ontolinguistics, stages of speech generation.

In the mid-20th century, fundamental works on child psychology by L.S. Vygotsky, A. Wallon, J. Piaget, and J. Bresner were published and gained worldwide renown, clarifying a number of complex issues in genetic psychology. Scientific priority in developing the foundations of the ontogenesis of the human psyche belongs to L.S. Vygotsky (1896–1934), who demonstrated ways to overcome the two-factor approach to understanding the determination of child development characteristic of traditional schools of psychology. L.S. Vygotsky argued that a child's intellectual development tightly intertwines verbal and practical thinking and depends on their balanced development. He understood the generation of a verbal utterance as the transition from thought to word. Vygotsky developed a model of speech production that still has numerous supporters today. Firstly, Vygotsky identified inner speech as a special

internal plane of verbal thinking, the subsequent dynamic relationship between thought and word; secondly, he believed that inner speech is characterized by:

- lack of phonation (pronunciation of sounds);
- predicativeness (subjects are often omitted, predicates predominate);
- collapse (no words).

Vygotsky, following Karl Bühler (1879-1963), a researcher of the early manifestations of children's practical thinking, considers the age of 6-7 months to be the beginning of the first manifestations of practical intelligence, which are completely independent of speech. Modern child psychology and psychiatry (led by Mikhail Ivanovich Buyanov, Thomas Bauer, and D. Elkonin) confirm the precedence of practical (instrumental) thinking before the first rudiments of speech in children, constituting the most genetically primary phase in the development of intelligence. However, modern psychiatry has experimentally confirmed a much earlier manifestation of instrumental intelligence. As early as 2.5 months, and even as young as 2 months (!), children in experiments could turn the light above their crib on and off by turning their heads in specific directions and establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the head turn and the light turning on. They could also find and pick up an object in the dark if they saw it a few seconds before the light turned off, in the same place where they later retrieved it.

Vygotsky's ideas were further developed by the Russian psychologist A. R. Luria (1902-1977), who studied neuropsychology, particularly the problem of higher psychophysiological mechanisms in localized brain disorders. Luria developed the theory of the dynamic schema of utterance as part of the utterance conception stage. The central component of Luria's model is the transition from meaning to significance. It was proposed that the formation of a speech utterance proceeds through several stages:

1. The stage of primary "semantic notation," which has the character of a condensed semantic utterance, which must subsequently be transformed into a system of sequentially linked words. Semantic notation necessarily contains a theme and rheme, which form the "initial thought." The transformation of initial schemata from condensed and unarticulated to expanded is accomplished through inner speech.

Stage 2. The collapsed structures of internal meaning are recoded, using inner speech, into the structure of a future expanded syntactic utterance.

Stage 3. Formation of an expanded speech utterance.

According to Luria, mastering speech presupposes the generation of an expanded speech utterance.

The concepts of the Russian psychological school of linguistics (A.N. Leontiev, L.S. Vygotsky, A.R. Luria) were further developed in the research of A. Leontiev, one of the leading Russian psycholinguists. Thus, the concept of activity became the scientific basis for L.S. Vygotsky's theory of speech activity. A.A. Leontiev agrees with A.R. Luria in his propositions about the stage-by-stage nature of speech formation and that the process of speech production is an integral part of a holistic act of activity. A theory of speech production is proposed:

Stage 1. Internal programming of the utterance, based on an image with personal meaning. Operations of inclusion, enumeration, and articulation are performed on programming units.

Stage 2. The stage of grammatical-semantic implementation. A number of substages are distinguished:

- textual and grammatical;
- phonological (linear distribution of code units);
- syntactic prediction (assigning grammatical characteristics to elements);
- syntactic control (correlating "predictions with the situation").

Stage 3. Motor programming.

Stage 4. Speech implementation.

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